

SMART MULTI-FUNCTIONAL CARBON NANOTUBE/POLY(VINYL ALCOHOL) COMPOSITE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Wearable smart textiles that have functionalities like sensor, actuator, and electromagnetic shielding are becoming increasing interesting research field due to the proliferation of modern society's demand for wearable electronics and protection of environmental electromagnetic pollution. The development of nanotechnology makes these smart textile composites available. Here, we report two types of smart nano-composite fiber which can be used as textile humidity sensor and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding performance.

Textile-based humidity sensors can be an important component of smart wearable electronic-textiles and have potential applications in the management of wounds, bed-wetting, and skin pathologies or for microclimate control in clothing. Several approaches have been previously conducted to transfer conventional capacitive and resistive humidity sensors onto textiles. However, major challenges remain to be overcome. For example, the durability of electrodes prepared by printing and deposition remains an important issue to be addressed. In addition, the sensitivity of sensors made of conductive yarn electrodes depends strongly on the wettability of the textile substrate into which the electrodes are woven, which may limit these sensors' applications. To solve these challenges, we fabricate a wearable textile-based humidity sensors using high strength (~750 MPa) and ultra-tough (energy-to-break, 4300 J g⁻¹) single-walled carbon nanotube (SWNT)/poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) filaments using a wet-spinning process. The conductive SWCNT networks in the filaments can be modulated by adjusting the intertube distance by swelling the PVA molecular chains via the absorption of water molecules. Textile-based humidity sensors using a 1:5 weight ratio of SWCNT/PVA filaments showed high sensitivity and excellent reversibility under different relative humidity conditions. We also demonstrated that our sensor can be used to monitor human sweating.

Magnetic nano-composite fibers are the topic of intense research due to their potential breakthrough applications such as smart magnetic field response devices and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding. However, clustering of nanoparticles in polymer matrix is a recognized challenge for obtaining a property-controllable nano-composite fiber. Another challenge is that the strength and ductility of the nano-composite fiber decrease significantly with the increasing weight loading of

magnetic nanoparticles in the fiber. Here, we report high-strength SWNT/permalloy nano-particle (PNP)/PVA multi-functional nano-composite fibers fabricated by wet spinning. The weight loading of SWNT and PNP in the fiber were as high as 12.0% and 38.0%, respectively. The tensile strength of the fiber was up to 700 MPa. The electrical conductivity reached 96.7 S/m. The saturation magnetization was as high as 24.8 emu/g. The EMI attenuation of a fabric woven from the prepared fiber approached to 100%, when tested by electromagnetic wave with a frequency higher than 6 GHz. Our study demonstrates that a magnetic field response device can be designed by using the fabricated multi-functional nano-composite fiber. These smart textiles pave a new way for the design of novel wearable smart textiles.